

EJP SOIL
European Joint Programme

**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

Deliverable 3.8

List of selected proposals of 3rd internal call

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

BPM	Board of programme Managers
MXX	EJP SOIL project months
WP	Work package

1. Submitted and evaluated proposals

1.1. General overview

The EJP SOIL will maximize the contribution of agricultural soil towards achieving sustainability at societal, scientific, operational, and policy level. At the scientific level the EJP SOIL will i) quantify trade-offs and synergies between agricultural production, climate change adaptation and mitigation, ii) assess and validate practices to maintain soil fertility, soil health and other ecosystem services, iii) gather new knowledge on carbon sequestration in soils across Europe and their contribution to climate change mitigation, and iv) improve accounting and reporting tools for emission and removals from agricultural activities. Activities aiming to develop required knowledge will be supported by the EJP SOIL through specific research and innovation projects *via* internal (i.e., WP3 “Internal Calls”) and external EJP SOIL calls. The overall objective of the 3rd internal call has been to fund research projects open to EJP SOIL beneficiaries and linked third parties to fill research and development gaps identified by the “Roadmap for the European Joint Program SOIL” and the annual work program of the EJP SOIL for year three. The call topics are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Topics of the EJP SOIL` 3rd Internal Call

Topic title	ID*	Number of projects and their size [#]
Identifying adaptation options, related to agricultural soil management, to respond to water-related impacts of extreme weather and climate change	CA2	1, medium
Mitigate and adapt to salinization and restore saline soils: understanding the processes and improving cropping systems under current and future climate	SE5	1, medium
Soil futures: scenario modelling for assessing the potential of climate-smart sustainable soil management to provide multiple ecosystem services	SE6	1, medium
Soil specific guidelines and decision support tools with focus on soil organic matter, water retention and nutrient use efficiency	AD3	1, medium
Healthy and safe soils in the agro-ecological transitions towards a circular bioeconomy	POL3	1, medium
Contribution of soils to climate change mitigation and adaptation, sustainable agricultural production and environment in agroecological systems	CA4/SP3-1	1, medium
Fostering the adoption of agroecological systems for climate change mitigation and adaptation and sustainable agricultural production	CA4/SP3-2	1, medium

* Third Internal Call Text, D3.7. EJP SOIL topic ID: CA Climate change adaptation; SE Sustainable Environment; SP Sustainable Production; AD Adoption of sustainable soil management; POL Science policy interface.

[#] Third Internal Call Text, D3.7

The WP3 Call Office published the call topics in the full call text in M27 (Table 2). Submission deadline was on 15th of June 2022. The call office received 7 proposals addressing the call topics (Tables 1 and 3). Most project proposals have been submitted by coordinators from Central Europe (71%; Table 3),

one from Eastern Europe and one from Southern Europe, but none of the submitted project proposals were coordinated by an EJP SOIL member from Northern Europe. A brief overview of the submitted projects is shown in Table 4 and at the end of this section (i.e., the project summaries drafted by the applicants). All proposals passed the eligibility check (Table 5). Eligible proposals were reviewed by external evaluators between 22nd of June and 31st of August. Final selection was done by the BPM in M32. Selected projects started in November 2022.

Table 2: Timeline of the EJP SOIL's 3rd internal call

Action	Project calendar	Schedule
Call pre-announcement	M26	28 March 2022
Launch of the call	M27	1 April 2022
2 nd Webinar for interested applicants	M27	7 April 2022
Workshops for interested participants	M27	April 2022
Closing date for proposal submission	M29	15 June 2022
Proposal evaluation and selection	M29-32	June - September 2022
Notification letters sent to project coordinators	M33	October 2022
Grant preparation	M33	October 2022
Start of research projects	M34	November 2022
End of research projects	M57	October 2024

Table 3: Number of proposals submitted per call topics; proposal coordinator and country; and regions of their home country

Topic ID	Number of applications	Proposal coordinator	European region
CA2	2	AGS / Switzerland NPPC / Slovakia	Central/West East
SE5	0	-/-	-
SE6	1	AGS / Switzerland	Central/West
AD3	1	WR / Netherlands	Central/West
POL3	1	WR / Netherlands	Central/West
CA4/SP3-1	1	AGS / Switzerland	Central/West
CA4/SP3-2	1	CSIC / Spain	South
Total	7		

Table 4: Proposals submitted and validated by BPM for funding; the type, estimated budget and number of beneficiaries and linked third parties (LTP).

EJP ID	Acronym	Title	Proposal co-ordinator	Type	Budget in kEUR	Number of beneficiaries	Number of LTP	Total number
CA2	Sloix	Soil management to mitigate climate change-related precipitation extremes	AGS / Switzerland	medium	1,733	5	1	6
SE6	SIMPLE	Scenario modelling for assessing impacts of policy changes and socio-economic effects on ecosystem services of soils	AGS / Switzerland	medium	1,559	7	0	7
AD3	PRAC2LIV	Fostering soil management PRACTices uptake and developing decision support TOols through LIVing labs in EU	WR / Netherlands	medium	0,676	24	1	25
POL3	BioCASH	Bio-economy and Circular Agriculture for Soil Health	WR / Netherlands	medium	1,243	8	0	8
CA4/SP3-1	ARTEMIS	Agro-ecological strategies for promoting climate change Mitigation and Adaptation by enhancing soil ecosystem services and sustainable crop production	AGS / Switzerland	medium	1,783	8	4	12
CA4/SP3-2	Into-	More than a Dialogue between actors, seeking the integration of soil-based principles in agroecological systems	CSIC / Spain	medium	0,914	7	1	8

Each project proposal was briefly described by the applicants; see their summaries below:

CA2 SoilX: SoilX seeks to improve the evidence base on management impacts on water regulation functions of the soil and crop response by measuring soil hydraulic and mechanical properties in long-term field experiments with histories of alternative treatments across Europe. Multi-model simulation experiments evaluate potential adaptation benefits as well as mitigation/sustainability co-benefits to be achieved through soil structural changes under current and future climate conditions. Qualitative interviews with farmers identify context-dependent inhibiting/enabling factors for the uptake of beneficial soil management practices. Synthesized project findings will improve the basis of knowledge and evidence to provide better soil management advice for both farmers and policy makers in Europe.

SE6 SIMPLE: Agricultural soils provide a wide array of ecosystem services that need to be maintained and enhanced if agriculture is to be made more sustainable and climate-friendly. Building on carbon sequestration rates provided by the CarboSeq project, we expand the potential for climate-smart soil management through reductions in fertilization rates to decrease N₂O emissions and to comply with the Farm to Fork Strategy. Potential trade-offs on soil carbon storage will be analyzed using a modelling framework that links soil carbon modelling with nitrogen flow and agro-economic modelling. Our results will identify risks and benefits of reduced fertilization and support the selection of best measures. The modelling framework will serve as a basic structure for scenario modelling in future studies.

AD3 PRAC2LIV: The project PRAC2LIV will make and evaluate a stock-take of Decision Support Tools (DSTs) that focus on soil organic matter, water retention, and nutrient use efficiency as currently used by EJP Member States. Building on previous stocktakes, EU-projects and national reports, the overview will include DSTs from simple tools to the next generation level support systems. Both the scientific base of DSTs as well as their implementation and adoption at farm level will be assessed, with special attention for soil management practices, regional distance-to-target options, and data sharing for web-portal applications. Guidelines for development of DSTs and designs for (mock-up) web-portal and/or dashboards will be discussed in workshop exchanges with stakeholder groups, e.g., living labs and/or EU-lighthouse projects. Based on the results from the stocktake and these discussions, a tiered approach will be developed for future development of DSTs in agro-systems across EJP Member States.

POL3 BioCASH: The key research question guiding BioCASH is how resource management can be optimized to close nutrient, energy and biomass circles which integrate urban composts and green wastes in multi-purpose agro-ecological production systems that is economically viable, socially acceptable and long-term sustainable beyond the agricultural sector. Soil health is here an important criterion for assessing sustainability. To address this research question, BioCASH aims at creating a modelling framework at micro level that enable scaling up of biocircular supply chains of waste streams from the level of selected and site-specific production systems to landscape level. From the soil perspective, the toolbox should consider the evaluation of indicators related to soil health (e.g., soil biodiversity, carbon sequestration, capacity of water retention, nutrient cycling) and safety (i.e., analysis of contaminants such as metals and microplastics). From the agronomic perspective, the toolbox should also translate the results on soil functions into soil fertility and the outcomes on plant growth. From the circularity perspective, cost benefit analysis and environmental footprint analysis of biocircular supply chains of waste streams should also be seen as model components in the toolbox. The combined use of existing modelling frameworks at macro level and the proposed modelling framework at micro level should be able to capture policies and drivers of large-scale structural changes on bioeconomy as well as agricultural transitions, and their consequential effects on soils functions.

CA4/SP3-1 ARTEMIS: Soils provide a multitude of ecosystem services that can contribute both, to the mitigation as well as adaptation to climatic change. Land management practices have a large effect on the ability of soils to provide these services. The project will provide a better understanding on how specific agro-ecological practices affect soil ecosystem service indicators and how these indicators can be assessed in the field. This will be achieved by the evaluation of regionally representative field experiments using numerical modelling, a literature survey as well as in direct exchange with practitioners.

CA4/SP3-2 Into-DIALOGUE: Into-DIALOGUE hypothesizes that the adoption of Sustainable Agroecological Systems as a whole is difficult to be achieved in European and Turkish agricultural landscapes in the short term, given the complexity of holistically adopting their assumptions. Into-DIALOGUE will provide an integrative multi-actor approach for the integration of soil-based systems, the ecological identity of farmers, the design of political measures, and the possibilities of collaboration offered by citizen participation to facilitate the transition.

1.2. Eligibility check

Each submitted proposal was evaluated by WP3 against eligibility criteria described in the EJP SOIL's 3rd call, section 3 (D3.7 with more details):

- The application must be written in English.
- Applications must be complete and in accordance with the submission procedure.
- Applications must be submitted in time.
- Proposals including beneficiaries and/or third linked parties that are NOT EJP SOIL beneficiaries are not eligible to apply and will be rejected.

As mentioned above, of the seven proposals, all passed the eligibility check, but coordinators of selected projects will be asked to revise for instance ethics and communication sections prior project start.

1.3. Evaluation results

WP3 built up a pool of external evaluators consisting of 19 experts (out of 90 who were invited for the 3rd call) who agreed to evaluate EJP SOIL project proposals and signed a non-disclosure agreement. The evaluators cover multiple disciplines (e.g., carbon sequestration, soil nutrients, agronomy, soil ecology, climate change) allowing discipline-specific evaluations. Each project proposal was evaluated by 3 external evaluators. For each proposal, experts presented their evaluation results in an individual evaluation report, explaining the evaluation scores. For each proposal one of the evaluators acted as a rapporteur who assessed all the individual evaluation reports within a call, to: 1) ensure that the evaluator group have been consistent in their evaluations; 2) if necessary, propose a new set of marks or comments; and 3) resolve cases where a consensus could not be reached.

The scoring gives information on the proposal's quality¹. As mentioned in the EJP SOIL's 3rd call (section 4.2; D3.7) a threshold of 3 out of 5 will be applied for each criterion, i.e., proposals with a mean score

¹ **0: Failure:** The proposal fails to address the criterion in question, or cannot be judged because of missing or incomplete information; **1: Poor:** The proposal shows serious weaknesses in relation to the criterion in question; **2: Fair:** The proposal generally addresses the criterion, but there are significant weaknesses that need corrections; **3: Good:** The proposal

<3 in any main criterion will not be recommended for funding. One of the projects received an average score of <3 in all of the evaluation criteria (i.e., Excellence, Impact, Implementation) and was not recommended for funding.

The request to fund eligible and the highest scoring (in their topic) project proposals was validated by the BPM on 18th of October 2022. SoilX, SIMPLE, PRAC2LIV, BioCASH, ARTEMIS and Into-DIALOGUE were approved for funding without further conditions. The project coordinators provided their replies to the evaluator comments to the following BPM meeting.

addresses the criterion in question well but certain improvements are necessary; **4: Very good:** The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but small improvements are possible; **5: Excellent:** The proposal successfully addresses all aspects of the criterion in question.

